

1. The Teaching Approach to Requirements Engineering

According to Pressman and Maxim (2021), the field of Software Requirements (SR) involves a range of techniques and activities designed to develop a thorough understanding of system requirements. Daun et al. (2021) reinforces the idea that Requirements Engineering (RE) has become an essential discipline within Software Engineering (SE), as proper handling of requirements contributes to the delivery of higher-quality software and significantly reduces the risk of project failure and budget overruns. Building on this, Ouhbi (2019) emphasizes that students should be able to elicit, analyze, specify, and validate explicit and implicit requirements from stakeholders with diverse backgrounds and profiles.

Adopting teaching and learning strategies in the classroom can significantly increase student motivation and engagement, as well as facilitate content assimilation by making students the protagonists of their own learning process. The authors emphasize that education in software requirements engineering (SRE) should not be restricted to teaching formal or informal specification of requirements. It is also essential that it involves practices and methodologies that prepare students to overcome challenges such as identifying and negotiating conflicts between requirements from different sources, meeting the specific needs of stakeholders, and resolving other technical issues inherent in the process.

Taking this context into account, the teaching approach adopted for Software Requirements was structured according to the process described in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The process of building the teaching approach.

Initially, documentary research was conducted on the Pedagogical Course Projects (PPC) of Computer Science courses in Brazil, based on data from the most recent National Student Performance Examination (ENADE). The objective was to identify the content present in the course syllabuses and analyze how it corresponded to the topics defined in the Software Engineering Body of Knowledge guide (SWEBOK), specifically in the Software Requirements knowledge area (Sandro and Oliveira, 2025).

After completion of this initial stage, a systematic literature review (SLR) was conducted to identify teaching approaches, tools, evaluation strategies, and methodologies applied to teaching Software Requirements. This SLR aimed to provide an exhaustive and impartial synthesis of existing research in this area by adopting rigorous and reproducible methods to minimize bias and ensure the reliability of the findings. The results of this review were published in (Santos and Oliveira, 2024a).

Following the completion of the SLR, an analysis was conducted of the main reference documents used in the development of Computer Science curricula, including the Brazilian Computer Society's Computing Education Framework (RF-CC-2017 SBC), the Computing Curricula (CC-2020), and the SWEBOK. At this stage, the competencies and content present in the reference curricula of the Brazilian Computer Society (SBC) and the Association for Computing Machinery/Institute of Electrical and Electronic Engineers (ACM/IEEE), as well as SWEBOK 3.0, were identified and selected. The results of this analysis were published in (Santos and Oliveira, 2024b).

Once the asset mapping and SLR stages had been completed, the curriculum was structured and the teaching plan developed to meet the demands of the proposed curriculum. This phase was based on studies by Elgrably and Oliveira (2020) and Quaresma and Oliveira (2022), who proposed curricular models in other areas of software engineering. The resulting structure was published in (Santos and Oliveira, 2024c).

Finally, the experiment was conducted and applied to a class in the Bachelor's degree program in Software Engineering at a higher education institution. The focus was on implementing the developed curriculum and teaching plan using active methodologies that had been selected in advance. Then a qualitative evaluation of the experiment was carried out using a SWOT analysis of the teaching approaches adopted. The presentation of the results of this evaluation is the main objective of this article.

2. The Curriculum and the Teaching Plan

The curriculum used in the experiment was organized by competencies and content, focusing on topics defined by the SWEBOK guide, which provides greater technical detail on topics in Software Engineering. The structure was divided into four interdependent didactic units: I. Fundamentals of Software Requirements Engineering; II. Requirements Elicitation Techniques; III. Analysis and Specification of Requirements; and IV. Management and Maintenance of Requirements. This structure ensures a logical and formative progression of knowledge for students throughout the course. In addition, a teaching plan was developed that details course objectives, expected results, technologies used, activity schedule, evaluation methods, and pedagogical strategies. Presented at the beginning of the experiment, this plan served as a guide for professors and students alike, promoting alignment and transparency throughout the course.

Each unit was carefully planned and included guiding questions, prerequisites, program content (SWEBOK Guide), and expected results aligned with Bloom's revised taxonomy. Unit I introduces fundamental Software Requirements concepts, such as the distinction between functional and nonfunctional requirements. Unit II dives deeper into elicitation techniques, highlighting practices such as interviews, observation, and document analysis. Unit III aims to equip students with the skills to perform requirements analysis and specification based on conceptual modeling techniques and the creation of formal documents. Finally, Unit IV addresses requirements management and maintenance, focusing on aspects such as traceability, validation, and change management.

In terms of teaching strategies, several active methodologies were implemented based on the SLR. Notable examples include the combination of theoretical and practical classes, project-based learning (PBL), the flipped classroom, and the application of dynamic and gamification elements. These strategies aimed to promote participatory, critical, and student-centered learning, strengthening the practical application of the knowledge acquired during the course.

PBL played a key role in this approach, in which students organized themselves into groups to simulate fictitious companies with real software requirements. Throughout the course, each group developed a complete requirements project, carrying out continuous activities of gathering, analyzing, specifying, and managing, with periodic deliveries of work products in a virtual learning environment.

In Teaching Unit I, the groups structured their projects by defining the field of activity of the created company, the software requirement, and the initial scope of the application. They clearly described the problem, its impact, and the proposed solution. In Teaching Unit II, students applied two requirements elicitation techniques, meticulously documenting their execution and justifying the choices made for system development.

In Teaching Unit III, requirements were analyzed and specified, including their classification and conceptual modeling through use case, class, and activity diagrams. In Teaching Unit IV, the groups managed and maintained requirements, developed system prototypes, defined acceptance tests, and created a traceability matrix, thus completing the project in an integrated and practical way.

The Flipped Classroom methodology was adopted to improve the understanding of specific content, particularly the techniques for eliciting requirements, and to encourage students to prepare for presentations and discussions in advance. This approach favored a student-centered teaching and learning process and was implemented at the beginning of Teaching Unit II with the same groups that had been formed for PBL.

In this setup, each group was responsible for presenting two software requirements elicitation techniques, selected by lottery, as well as the order of the presentations. On the day of the presentations, the professor evaluated the groups based on criteria such

as the clarity and relevance of the content, the theoretical depth, the level of preparation, the effectiveness of the teaching strategies, and the quality of the material presented.

Gamification acted as an incentive in the proposed approach, contributing to student engagement throughout the course. Although it did not directly assign grades, game elements such as ranking, real-time feedback, participation monitoring, and progression were used to promote motivation and healthy competition between students. This strategy, in conjunction with other active methodologies, aimed to make the teaching and learning process more dynamic and effective, and to align it with the current demands of training in computer science courses.

The first dynamic applied was the Interrogation Dynamic, which aimed to increase student engagement, assess understanding of Teaching Unit I content, and stimulate critical thinking. The students were divided into teams and given time to develop questions exploring different cognitive levels. The professor acted as a mediator, evaluating the quality of the questions and creating a safe, participatory environment.

During the activity, the students formed a circle. A student was placed in the center and questioned by members of the other teams in an order determined by drawing lots. After each answer, the professor provided immediate feedback, promoting discussion, correcting misconceptions, and encouraging participation from everyone, especially the more timid students. In the end, the main points addressed were summarized to reinforce the learning and clarify any remaining doubts.

The second activity, Dojo Randori, focused on collaboratively developing conceptual modeling of a system based on its requirements, including use case, class, and activity diagrams. The students worked in pairs, taking turns periodically while the class observed and developed strategies. Finally, the professor and students reflected on the results, difficulties, and solutions adopted, emphasizing the importance of this practice for collective learning, exchanging experiences, and improving technical and collaborative skills.

More information on the curriculum and teaching plan on which the experiment was based, and the quality assessment of which is reported in this work, can be found in reference (Santos and Oliveira, 2024c).

3. Related Works

This section aims to present and analyze some related works on evaluation strategies and the results of case studies that involve the application of active methodologies in the teaching process.

One of the objectives of the study by Castro (2024) was to present the results of applying an approach based on active methodologies in the discipline of Systems Analysis and

Design, based on a qualitative evaluation. Two evaluation strategies were adopted for this purpose: the first involved the use of HappyIndex after the application of pre- and post-tests, and the second study was conducted using the 3L (Like, Learned, and Lacked) retrospective technique.

The work of Minhat et al. (2024) evaluated the teaching approach through an experiment using tests applied before and after the intervention. Among the indicators considered in the evaluation, the happiness index (HappyIndex) stood out. In (Costa et al., 2023), active methodologies were implemented in the course of Software Testing. To evaluate the approach, the authors used statistical analysis with a quantitative focus, while the qualitative evaluation was based on student reports.

Finally, the study by Quaresma and Oliveira (2022) implemented a curriculum based on active methodologies in the Software Processes course for a postgraduate program in Computer Science. The experience was qualitatively evaluated using the SWOT analysis technique. The same approach was adopted to obtain the results presented in this paper.

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